

DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERIZATION OF 3D C/C COMPOSITES FOR FUSION APPLICATIONS

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SUMMARY

3D titanium doped carbon fibre composites (CFCs) were developed and the influence of the dopant on the properties was studied. The materials were exposed to transient thermal loads. The CFC with the best behaviour was brazed to CuCrZr block using a Mo interlayer and thermal fatigue behaviour was studied.

Keywords: CFCs, Mesophase pitch, TiC, Thermal shock, Divertor

INTRODUCTION

CFCs have been proposed as plasma facing materials (PFMs) in ITER for the strike point area of the divertor due to their excellent thermo-mechanical properties [1]. In principle, plasma facing components (PFCs) are composed of stainless steel with embedded water coolant manifolds that carry an array of heat sinks. The heat flux is extremely high during off-normal conditions (several GW/m²), such as plasma disruptions, edge localized modes (ELMs) or vertical displacements events (VDE), but it is also significant during normal operating conditions (from 5 up to 20 MW/m²). Due to the extreme thermal loads deposited on the material, CFCs and carbon materials in general suffer macroscopic erosion called brittle destruction [2]. This phenomenon describes the release of particles (matrix or fibres) out of material surface due to the mechanical stresses caused by deposited heat loads on the material. As consequence, the protective material needs high thermal conductivity to transfer the heat load deposited on the surface and also because this reduces the thermally induced mechanical stresses. It has been demonstrated that the addition of TiC in graphites contributes to an effective improvement of thermal conductivity together with the improvement of the chemical erosion resistance under hydrogen bombardment, another of the main drawbacks of carbon materials [3].

EXPERIMENTAL

Development of the materials

A mesophase pitch (AR) commercialised by *Mitsubishi Gas Chemical* was used as matrix precursor to densify a 3D orthogonal framework supplied by *SGL Carbon Group* composed by pitch carbon fibres (x-direction) and PAN-based carbon fibres (y and z directions). The preforms were densified by liquid impregnation with the matrix precursor, either the mesophase pitch (AR) or the doped precursor, obtained through the mixture of the mesophase with 10 wt. % of TiC nanoparticles (80 nm) [4]. The densification process consisted on an initial step of vacuum up to 350°C followed by the application of a nitrogen pressure of 0.7 MPa for 4 hours. The densified preforms were submitted to a thermal process [5] prior to carbonisation at 1000°C, in order to reduce the fluidity of the precursor and therefore avoiding its exudation from the preform. Several densification cycles were applied and finally, the materials were graphitised at 2700°C. The undoped material was labelled as CFC, while Ti-CFC was used for the doped material. The resultant materials were characterised with respect to their microstructure and thermo-physical properties.

Electron beam thermal loads tests

The materials were exposed to transient thermal loads, disruptions, in the electron beam test facility JUDITH in order to simulate fusion operation conditions. The thermal shock tests were performed on specimens where pitch based fibre-bundles were aligned parallel to the heat transfer direction, while PAN fibre-bundles were aligned perpendicular to the heat transfer direction. Absorbed power densities at 1, 1.6 and 2.4 GW/m² during 5 ms pulses were performed at room temperature applying multiple shots (10 and 100). During the experiments a CCD-camera was used to monitor particle emission together with an absorbed current measurement to verify the absorbed power density and a fast pyrometer to measure the surface temperature on the materials. After the tests, the erosion depth was estimated using laser profilometry and optical microscopy. SEM was used to check the integrity of the material.

Fabrication of plasma facing component (mock-up) and thermal fatigue testing

An active cooled flat tile mock-up was developed with Ti-CFC. The brazing process was performed in Ansaldo Research. 3 tiles of 20x27x5 mm were brazed to CuCrZr heat sink blocks, using 2 mm thick Mo sheets as interlayer to produce the mock-up. Brazing was performed through a single vacuum heat treatment, during 18 minutes at 1035 °C, using Cu-ABA alloy on the CFC side and Gemco alloy on the CuCrZr one. The compounds were exposed to a “thermal shock test” consisting on heating up to 450°C followed by water quench to RT. Additionally, optical studies were performed to obtain a first indication about the quality of the components.

The mock-up was exposed to thermal fatigue tests in JUDITH, in order to study the thermal fatigue behaviour of the components, i.e. the joining technique and the materials themselves. Screening test and thermal cycling were applied. The screening test started in 2.5 MW/m² increasing up to 15 MW/m² in steps of 2.5 MW/m²

followed by thermal cycling at 15 MW/m² for 100 cycles. When possible, further screening tests were applied from 16 up to 20 MW/m² in steps of 1 MW/m² and followed by 100 cycles at 20 MW/m². Infra-red image, water calorimetry and pyrometer measurements were used to study the behaviour of the compound during the thermal loading and the formation of hot-spots (indicating failure). In post mortem analyses, optical microscopy of the cross section of the compound was used to identify the specific failure of the components.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The materials developed have around ~ 17 % total porosity (Table 1) which is entirely open porosity. Thermal conductivity was measured in the direction of highest thermal conductivity (x-direction). Both materials have very high thermal conductivity (>200W/mK), but it is significantly higher for the doped material due to the high catalytic activity of titanium on graphitisation (288W/mK).

Table1. Thermo-physical properties of the materials

Composites	Open porosity (%)	Close porosity (%)	Bulk density (g/cm ³)	Ti content in matrix (at.%)	Ti content in CFC (at.%)	Thermal conductivity (x-direction) (W/mK)
CFC	17	0	1.70	-	-	220
Ti-CFC	17	0	1.74	~3	0.6	288

Figure 1 shows optical micrographs of the Ti-CFC taken in x-direction. Cracks were formed during graphitisation and some differences had been observed between the undoped and the Ti-doped material. While in the case of the undoped material the cracks are present around pitch fibre-bundles, in the case of the Ti-CFC cracks pass through the bundles due to the different thermal expansion coefficient of the components (image a). Image (b) shows the good dispersion of TiC in the matrix, with sub-micrometric size. Finally (c) shows the high orientation degree of the matrix around the fibres, no debonding being observed between fibre and matrix, indicative of a strong bonding between them.

Figure1. SEM micrographs of Ti-CFC

Behaviour of the materials under transient thermal loads

When materials were exposed to disruption like conditions, preferential erosion of the PAN fibre-bundles aligned parallel to the loaded area (y and z directions) was observed (Figure 2a). This is a consequence of the local overheating caused by the lower thermal conductivity of these fibres and therefore inefficient heat dissipation from the surface to the bulk material. In the evolution of the erosion profiles, an increase in erosion depth of the PAN fibre layers with increasing power density was observed. The main erosion took place during the first shots, whereas later no particle erosion (brittle destruction) but only sublimation was observed, causing a slowdown of material erosion, as it previously was observed [6]. The erosion depth in PAN fibre-bundles is still under investigation. As a consequence of the local overheating of PAN fibres, erosion of pitch fibres was also observed in the transition zone between PAN and pitch fibre-bundles. Figure 2 (b) and (c) shows the microstructure of the pitch fibres in this zone exposed to 1.6 GW/m^2 for 5 ms and applying 100 shots.

Figure 2. SEM images: a) Ti-CFC eroded at 1.6 GW/m^2 , 5 ms, 10 x b) Ti-CFC and c) CFC, show pitch fibres close to the interphase PAN/pitch fibre-bundles at 1.6 GW/m^2 , 5 ms, 100 shots

Ti-CFC showed less eroded pitch fibres compared with the undoped material. In the doped material, the erosion in pitch fibres took place mainly by sublimation until a distance of $\sim 60 \mu\text{m}$ from the interface due to the overheating of PAN fibres. The erosion in the rest of the bundle was negligible (see upper left part in Figure 2b). A higher amount of eroded pitch fibres was found in the undoped CFC in the transition zone (distance from PAN/pitch interface: $\sim 120 \mu\text{m}$) and also slight erosion was observed in the centre of the pitch fibre bundles (see image 2c). The better behaviour of Ti-CFC is due to its higher thermal conductivity, which contributes to a better transfer of the heat deposited on the surface. Also, the TiC that agglomerated on surface of the material (mainly in the pores, see Figure 2a) could contribute to a shielding effect of the pitch fibres in the centre of the bundle. On the cross sections of the tested materials horizontally aligned cracks were observed close to the surface of pitch fibre-bundles. This corresponds to findings in reference CFCs tested in a Quasi-Stationary Plasma Accelerator [7]. As can be observed in Figure 3, the cracks are situated in a depth of $\sim 30\text{-}50 \mu\text{m}$. These cracks are probably caused by thermally induced stresses generated because of the temperature gradients in the material and the anisotropy of thermal expansion coefficient as well as the Young's Modulus.

Figure 3. Loaded area of Ti-CFC at 2.4 GW/m^2 , 5 ms and 100 shots: Cracks in pitch fibre-bundles

Mock-up fabrication and thermal fatigue testing

Due to the large thermal expansion mismatch between the CFC and the copper alloy, a thin 2 mm thick interlayer made of molybdenum was inserted between the CFC and the CuCrZr to reduce the joint interface stress. For a first qualification of the module it was exposed to 30 “thermal shocks” (water quenching from 450°C to room temperature). Optical examination after this treatment revealed neither cracks in the CFC nor detachments at the interfaces proving the high quality of the joint.

The compound was exposed to thermal fatigue test in JUDITH, one of the tiles surviving 100 cycles at 15 MW/m^2 followed by 62 cycles at 20 MW/m^2 . The other two suffered erosion during screening (achieving steady state condition and monitoring the cool down behaviour) between 15 and 20 MW/m^2 . This was causing the shutdown of the e-beam due to a short time loss of vacuum and therefore the loaded surface was reduced to one tile. Due to a continuous slight degradation of tile 1 and the repeated break down of vacuum, maybe due to bad sealing at the cooling tube or due to erosion of CFC, the test was stopped without complete failure of the tile. Erosion of the CFC in specific areas was observed due to surface overheating, as can be observed in Figure 4. The overheating is most probably caused by failure at the interface between CFC and Mo resulting from the above mentioned CTE mismatch and the applied temperature gradient in the component. The onset of failure is at the outer surface of the tiles and due to the occurring stress singularities at these positions. This as well as the fact that no hot spots were identified already during screening at low power densities, an incomplete joining process at one of the two interfaces can be excluded as detrimental failure parameter. In order to verify this, optical examination is being determined in the module in order to check the main failure mode.

Figure 4. Active cooled flat tile mock-up after thermal fatigue testing

CONCLUSIONS

The materials developed have very high thermal conductivity and the addition of TiC to the carbon matrix improved the thermal conductivity and significantly thermal shock resistance.

Both, the undoped and Ti-doped composites, showed a rather good behaviour during disruptions and an active cooled mock-up was developed with the best material. The results obtained with the mock-up during thermal fatigue tests let assume that Ti-CFC is a promising material as plasma facing material. However, the behaviour could be even significantly improved improving brazing technology and by reducing the porosity applying one more densification cycle by liquid impregnation and a final CVD treatment.

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REFERENCES

- [1] V. Barabash, M. Akiba, J. P. Bonal, G. Federici, R. Matera, K. Nakamura, H. D. Pacher, M. Rödiger, G. Vieider and C. H. Wu *Journal of Nuclear Materials* 258-263 (Part 1): 149-159. (1998).
- [2] H. Würz, B. Bazylev, I. Landman, S. Pestchanyi and V. Safronov *Journal of Nuclear Materials* 307-311(Part 1): 60-68. (2002).
- [3] C. García-Rosales, I. López-Galilea, N. Ordás, C. Adelhelm, M. Balden, G. Pintsuk, M. Grattarola and C. Gualco *Journal of Nuclear Materials* 386-388: 801-804. (2009).
- [4] A. Centeno, R. Santamaría, M. Granda, R. Menéndez and C. Blanco *Journal Materials Science*, (2009), DOI 10.1007/s10853-009-3327-9.A.
- [5] A. Centeno, R. Santamaría, M. Granda, R. Menéndez, C. Blanco *Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis*, In Press, Corrected Proof.
- [6] A. Centeno, C. Blanco, R. Santamaría, M. Granda, R. Menéndez, G. Pintsuk and J. Linke *Proceedings of International Conference on Carbon 2008*. Nagano (Japan) CD-ROM P0205.
- [7] K. Wittlich, T. Hirai, J. Compan, N. Klimov, J. Linke, A. Loarte, M. Merola, G. Pintsuk, V. Podkovyrov, L. Singheiser and A. Zhitlukhin *Fusion Engineering and Design* In Press, Corrected Proof.